

D1.1

Stakeholders' identification and needs

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Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
M1...M12	Month 1...Month 12
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
TEN-T	Trans-European Networks - Transport
EU	European Union
CT	Combined Transport
RTPD	Road Transport Posting Declaration Portal
IMI	Internal Market Information System
CMR	Convention relating to the "Contract for the International Transport of Goods by Road"
eFTI	electronic Freight Transport Information
WIM	Weight-In-Motion systems
OBW	On-Board Weighing equipment
HDV	Heavy Duty Vehicles
DG-MOVE	Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport
SEDEA	Single European Digital Enforcement Area
DTLF	Digital Transport and Logistics Forum
FENIX	European Federated Network of Information eXchange in LogistiX
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
B2B	Business to Business
A2A	Authority-to-Authority
MASP	Multi-annual Strategic Plan
SOA	Service-Oriented Architecture
EIF	European Interoperability Framework
UCC	Union Customs Code
EU CSW-CERTEX	EU Customs Single Window Certificates Exchange System
EUCDM	EU Customs Data Model
ECMT	European Conference of Ministers of Transport

UN/ECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
IM	Infrastructure Managers
RU	Railway Undertakings
RFP	Rail Facilities Portal
RNE	RailNetEurope
UIRR	Union Interantionale pour le transporte combine Rail-Route
MS	Member State
CMR	Carriage of Merchandise by Road
FIATA	International Federation of Freight Forwarders Associations
ESPO	European Sea Ports Organisation
IIFA	Irish International Freight Association
ERRU	European Register of Road Transport Undertakings
RESPER	RESeau PERmis de conduire

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1. Executive Summary

The purpose of this document is to present the results of T1.1, “Stakeholders' definition, needs and board implementation” that is part of WP1, “Gap Analysis and State of the Art”. WP1 started on M1 and will end in M12.

This document contains:

- an introduction to the topic of “Smart enforcement for road transport”, see Sect. 2
- a description of the main stakeholders, the creation of the KEYSTONE stakeholders' register, and the analysis of the KEYSTONE survey, see Sect. 3
- the final remarks and the conclusion of the deliverable, see Sect. 4
- the privacy policy for obtaining the explicit consent (GDPR compliant) from participants to be included in a register, see Annex 1
- the list of the questions included in the survey, see Annex 2

Finally, the work described in this document is linked to other tasks included in KEYSTONE project. This deliverable is expected to support:

- T1.2 (WP1) at introducing the state of the art and the requirements for the KEYSTONE solutions, at identifying gaps between the different competing.
- T1.3 (WP1) at analysing a of public and private electronic databases and exchange of information platforms, at analysing the existing digital platforms against the current legislative framework.
- T2.1 (WP2) at providing use cases, needs and requirements for developing the API reference model.
- T3.2 (WP3) at providing use cases, needs and requirements for developing the app user interface, at providing users for testing activities.
- T6.2 (WP6) at providing the list of stakeholders, external to the KEYSTONE project, to be engaged with.

2. Smart enforcement for road transport

2.1 Introduction

Freight transport and logistics play a crucial role for the competitiveness of the European economy and for the social cohesion of all regions of the Union. Since the 1990s, the European Union has supported the implementation of infrastructure projects to create a European market and develop economic and social cohesion. The trans-European transport networks (also known by the acronym "TEN-T", from the English "Trans-European Networks - Transport") were designed and built to make the movement of goods and people more efficient (https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/infrastructure-and-investment/trans-european-transport-network-ten-t_en), see Figure 1. On the other hand, the freight transport sector is one of the most responsible, after industry, for air pollution¹. Over the last decades, emissions produced by heavy-duty vehicles have progressively increased. In this regard, the European Parliament promulgated the so-called "Fit for 55" in 2020, a package of reforms and regulations, focused on the fight against climate change. It has set the ambitious goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by 55% compared to 1990 levels by 2030 and reaching climate neutrality in 2050.

Figure 1. Map of the Europe's TEN-T Core Network corridors

To make freight transport more efficient and sustainable while allowing the EU single market to keep growing, the European Commission has recently presented² a series of measures for ensuring greater sustainability

¹ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/topics/in-depth/transport-and-mobility>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-eurostat-news/w/wdn-20230515-1>

and promoting intermodal transport to keep freight traffic off the road. Even the European Court of Auditors recognized the importance of the intermodal tool³. Nevertheless, despite efforts to reduce road transport of goods, 77% of transport still takes place by road. According to the European Court of Auditors, the Commission's controls were hampered by the absence of data provided by member countries. Furthermore, the Combined Transport (CT) Directive (Council Directive 92/106/EEC) is obsolete (1992). This directive does not consider important needs, including, for example, the digitization of documents accompanying goods. The lack of information accessible in real time and relating to intermodal terminals and the capabilities of the network represents a critical issue to be addressed.

In addition to tackling climate change, the European Union aims to ensure the safe, efficient, sustainable, fair, and free movement of people and goods across the EU. So, the EU has developed a broad framework of rules applicable to the road transport sector. Such a framework provides (i) the minimum requirements that must be met by road transport operators, (ii) the rules that must be respected by professional drivers to guarantee road safety and (iii) the technical standards that must be respected by vehicles used for the commercial transport of goods or passengers. To guarantee the interconnection and interoperability of national road networks and facilitate the movement of goods and people within European territory, the European Union must be supported by a regulatory framework and by an adequate enforcement system. Compliance checks involve the collection, the verification, and the analysis of data relating to the (i) driver, (ii) vehicle, (iii) operator, (iv) load and (v) type of transport. Remotely or directly on the road, enforcement authorities (e.g., Port Authorities, Customs Agencies, Road Police, etc.) need to carry out the checks by accessing specific databases (e.g., shared from national authorities) that store relevant documents. The European Commission has been working to transform these documents into a machine-readable electronic format. For example, Directive (EU) 2020/1057 establishes that a driver can present a posting declaration in an electronic version. By the Road Transport Posting Declaration Portal (RTPD), road transport operators can connect to the Internal Market Information System (IMI) and submit electronically the necessary information about drivers that will be posted to another Member States. Furthermore, by a scan-on-the-road tool, roadside inspectors can scan a QR code from the driver's posting declaration and access all the details of the declaration allowing to check its authenticity and validity.

According to the Convention on the Contract for the international Carriage of goods by Road (CMR) delivery notes have been gradually replaced by electronic documents (e-CMR). To promote the usage of electronic documents, the EU regulation 2020/1056 established the obligation for the Authorities to accept information relating to the movement of goods in electronic format (eFTI - electronic Freight Transport Information). Data must be transmitted to the Authorities via secure platforms (eFTI) certified in accordance with the requirements of this regulation. eFTI platforms will allow reliable communications between companies and authorities, guaranteeing the authenticity, integrity and security of the data processed. In recent years, innovative devices have been developed for enhancing the efficiency and effectiveness of controls. Relevant examples are represented by the 'tachograph' (made mandatory in the vehicles engaged in the carriage of goods or passengers) and by the weight-in-motion (WIM) systems, or by means of on-board weighing equipment (OBW). The tachograph allows for recording and controlling driving time and other work, breaks, rest and availability periods of drivers. WIM systems are set-up on the road infrastructure and allow to automatically control compliance with the requirements on weights and dimensions of heavy-duty vehicles (HDV). Finally, OBW systems are installed in the vehicles.

Despite the introduction of new technologies and sophisticated devices, the logistic sector is still represented by a complex and difficult to harmonize ecosystem of stakeholders. The road transport law enforcement needs a boost. Digitalization, information, and communication technologies can address many challenges that current enforcement system faces.

Shift from paper to electronic documents means shifting from random to targeted controls. This is a great opportunity for both businesses and authorities to gain efficiency and transparency, reduce administrative burden and costs. Digitizing information related to the 'controlled' (driver, vehicle, operator, cargo), ensuring

³ <https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications?did=63659>

trustworthy access to real-time data and secure exchange of the data, as well as introducing automated control and analytical processes are crucial for creating a modern road transport ‘plug-and-play’ enforcement system. It would allow for risk-based controls, contactless and paperless, if possible remote inspections as well as streamlined control procedures which would render enforcement activities less burdensome, less time consuming, less costly, and more efficient. By exploiting digital data (related to ‘the controlled’) and automated procedures (used by ‘the controllers’ and ‘the controlled’), vehicles (while in motion) which need to be stopped for a comprehensive roadside control can be pre-selected. Furthermore, non-compliant operators for comprehensive controls at premises can be pre-identified.

KEYSTONE project aims at enhancing digitalization, information, and communication technologies for addressing the challenges currently faced by enforcement authorities. In the next sections, the main projects related to the objectives and to the activities of KEYSTONE are described.

2.2 Related projects

Under the Horizon Europe Framework, several projects (e.g., SETO⁴, DELPHI⁵) have been funded to develop systems for accessing real-time digitized information to help enforcement. The Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport (DG MOVE⁶) has also launched a call to understand steps for establishing a Single European Digital Enforcement Area (SEDEA⁷), which intends to identify and assess different models of smart enforcement systems.

Led by DG MOVE, the DTLF⁸ (Digital Transport and Logistics Forum) group focuses on promoting the digital transformation of the transport and the logistics sector. Since 2015 the DTLF assists the Commission in the development and implementation of the Union’s relevant activities and programmes, particularly those targeted at full-scale digital interoperability and data exchange in a shared, secured, and trusted transport and logistics dataspace. Furthermore, the DTLF contributes to the development of the Mobility Data Space, namely an important initiative in the framework of the European Common Data Spaces proposed in the European Data Strategy⁹. The activities carried out from the DTLF are divided in three different subgroups:

1. “*Subgroup 1 – Paperless Transport*”. Nowadays, paper has become an inefficient means for exchanging information. Yet paper documents and plastic cards (such as the driver’s licence) are still used for proving compliance with transport rules and with contractual agreements. During the period 2015-2018 this subgroup assisted the European Commission in defining and implementing initiatives that would replace the use of (paper) documents with electronic information exchanges for proving compliance with transport rules. Currently, the DTLF experts are assisting the Commission in exploring and preparing options for the implementation specifications of the eFTI Regulation (see 2.2.2)
2. “*Subgroup 2 – Corridor Freight Information System*”. Stakeholders operating in supply and logistics suffer and face the lack of interoperability and fragmentation of various data sharing systems. This subgroup was established to create a common framework for information sharing in multimodal transport and logistics chains. Existing or emerging platforms are going to be merged into a federated network, allowing all private and public players to easily connect and share data in a neutral and trusted environment. The future federated network of platforms should:
 - a. provide concepts and procedures that allow individual stakeholders to connect and share data according to common agreements (“Plug and Play”)
 - b. support common processes, business interoperability and compliance of business with legislation (“Technology Independent Services”)

⁴ SETO: <https://setoproject.eu/>

⁵ DELPHI: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/how-to-participate/org-details/999999999/project/101104263/program/43108390/details>

⁶ DG MOVE: https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/organisation/dg-move-dg-mobility-transport_en

⁷ SEDEA: <https://etendering.ted.europa.eu/cft/cft-display.html?cftId=11628>

⁸ DTLF: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/digital-transport-and-logistics-forum-dtlf_en#about-the-dtlf

⁹ European Data Strategy: https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy_en

- c. create (technical, functional, and business model) interoperability between different platforms, even when each platform is realized with different technology (“Federation”)
 - d. ensure trust, safety, and security for data sharing via multiple providers of platform services, including peer-to-peer solutions (“Trusted, Safe and Secure”)
3. “Subgroup 3 - Electronic Freight Transport Information (eFTI) Delegated Acts”. Entered into force on 20 August 2020, the implementation of Regulation (EU) No 2020/1056 on electronic freight transport information¹⁰ is one of the main initiatives for the digital transition in transport and logistics. Paperless freight transport by 2030 is one of the milestones of the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy.

Two EU funded projects are aimed at supporting the work of the “Subgroup 2”: FEDeRATED and FENIX, see Sect. 2.2.1. Section 2.2.2 contains more details about the introduction of electronic Freight Transport Information.

2.2.1 FENIX & FEDeRATED

FENIX (European Federated Network of Information eXchange in LogistiX)¹¹ has been co-financed by the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) of the European Union. Launched in 2019, the project has involved a total of 46 beneficiaries by implementing 11 different Pilot Sites across the European Union. After 48 months, FENIX has ended its journey. FENIX has worked to develop the first European federated architecture for data sharing serving the European logistics community of shippers, logistics service providers, mobility infrastructure providers, cities, and authorities to offer interoperability between any individual existing and future platforms. FENIX worked at creating a viable and valid federative network of platforms as enabler for Business to Administration (B2A) and Business to Business (B2B) data exchange and sharing by transport and logistics operators. FENIX has managed to leverage the interoperability-driven modelling framework along with existing model mechanisms and results from the H2020 projects AEOLIX¹² and SELIS¹³ as building blocks. The end goal of each pilot site was to set integrated services that exploit real-time Big Data streams for real time awareness and visibility, delivered from the cloud as a service. In practice, FENIX activities have focused on:

- Overcoming today’s fragmentation and lack of connectivity around ICT-based systems for logistics decision making.
- Interconnecting the different digital platforms and harmonise the services they offer.
- Ensuring interoperability and common protocols for supporting data sharing services.
- Enabling data sharing in the form of digital corridor information systems serving the European logistics community.

On the other hand, Semantics is at the core of the FEDeRATED project¹⁴. Co-funded by the European Commission Connecting Europe Facility (CEF), the project shall run until 29 December 2023. Data sharing is, to some extent, already supported by existing standards, platforms, and IT solutions. However, all these systems and initiatives have been designed and developed independently and uncoordinatedly. There are still too many bilateral agreements, proprietary solutions, and different platforms preventing a data sharing solution like the Internet functionality: one registration and connection to only one platform. Through harmonized data interoperability the various parties within the supply chain are allowed to seamlessly exchange digital information for multimodal freight transport business transactions as well as compliance to regulations¹⁵. For this purpose, FEDeRATED has been developed a semantic model, namely a representation of semantics by semantic web standards. FEDeRATED has been designing a federated network of platforms according to:

¹⁰ Regulation (EU) No 2020/1056 on electronic freight transport information: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R1056>

¹¹ FENIX: <https://fenix-network.eu/>

¹² AEOLIX: <https://aeolix.eu/>

¹³ SELIS: <https://selisproject.eu/>

¹⁴ FEDeRATED: <https://www.federatedplatforms.eu/>

¹⁵ FEDeRATED regulations: https://www.federatedplatforms.eu/images/Library/Activity2/TechnicalSpecs/1_Technical_Specifications_Semantics.pdf

- Open and de facto standards based on a common semantic model.
- The definition of organisational, functional, and technical specifications for a federated network of platforms for the entire Core Network in real life operational conditions.
- The development and validation of the federative network of platforms along various EU transport Core Network Corridors.
- The collaboration with relevant stakeholders including standardization bodies, software developers and platform providers.

2.2.2 eFTI4EU

eFTI4EU¹⁶ is the first European-level project aimed at implementing the EU Regulation 2020/1056¹⁷ relating to electronic information on freight transport (eFreight Transport Information). Financed under the Connecting Europe Facility (CEF) program of the European Commission, the project will create an efficient logistics network and will facilitate the digitalisation of freight transport through the sharing of information in electronic format between private operators and public administrations. eFTI4EU is a cooperation of a pan-European consortium of 22 partners, including 9 Member States (Estonia, Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal). The aim of the project is to create a unified approach to the operation of eFTI Gates, and to implement a reference architecture for exchanging logistics and transport data, which will be piloted through a series of use cases (both at national and cross-border level) in all the 9 Member States directly involved.

The eFTI regulation will apply from 21 August 2024: the electronic information processed on a certified eFTI platform and by a certified eFTI service provider will have to be accepted by authorities for control purposes. It will become fully applicable as of August 2025. Currently, technical architecture for eFTI is being developed, data elements and standard model for electronic exchange are being identified. Other digital initiatives of the EU (such as e-delivery, e-ID, EU Mobility Data Space etc.) are being leveraged. At this purpose, the European Commission has issued an initiative¹⁸ for collecting feedback. This implementing act sets out harmonized procedures, rules, and technical specifications to be followed by competent authorities of EU countries to access the eFTI platforms of transport operators. The aim is to guarantee that any eFTI platform can be accessed by the competent authorities of any EU country and to assure transport operators that the competent authorities handling their data are properly identified, authenticated, and authorized. The eFTI Regulation establishes the legal framework for electronic information exchanges between the economic operators and the Member States authorities on the movement of cargo in the European Union. The Regulation will bring important benefits to both operators and authorities:

- Reduced administrative costs in transport and logistics.
- Improved overall efficiency of the logistics chain, as it will also facilitate the electronic exchange of information between the economic operators themselves.
- More efficient enforcement of freight transport rules in the Union, by facilitating risk-based controls and ensuring the availability of more data of high and standardized quality that could be used for monitoring and statistical purposes.

The eFTI Regulation will complement other EU initiatives supporting freight information exchanges in electronic format, in particular the European Maritime Single Window environment¹⁹ and the EU Single Window Environment for Customs²⁰, see Sect. 2.2.3.

¹⁶ eFTI4EU: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/efti4eu-project/>

¹⁷ Regulation (EU) No 2020/1056 on electronic freight transport information: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R1056>

¹⁸ Initiative of the European commission: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/13661-Electronic-freight-transport-information-eFTI-procedures-and-access-rules-for-competent-authorities_en

¹⁹ European Maritime Single Window environment : <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32019R1239>

²⁰ EU Single Window Environment for Customs: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/eu-single-window-environment-customs_en

2.2.3 Electronic customs

Initiated by the European Commission, the Electronic customs project²¹ aims to replace paper-format customs procedures with EU-wide electronic procedures to create a more efficient and modern customs environment. The project has the objective to (i) enhance security at the EU's external borders and (ii) facilitating trade. The Customs Union²² (1 July 1968) is one of the pillars of the European Union and is at the heart of the internal market. It has provided a stable foundation for economic integration and growth in Europe for nearly five decades. Since its completion, the role played by customs and the working methods and processes have changed substantially to accommodate to the increasing volumes of world trade (see Figure 2), rapidly changing technologies and business models and persistent transnational crime and security threat. Paper format customs procedures have been gradually replaced by electronic ones.

According to the decision N. 70/2008/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council (15 January 2008), a basic framework for creating a paperless environment for customs and trade was set. Subsequently, the Commission drafted a plan which sets down the vision, objectives, the strategic framework, and the milestones to implement the electronic customs initiative, the Multi-annual Strategic Plan (MASP)^{23 24}. The MASP currently contains descriptions of approximately 30 projects. Examples of these projects include centralised customs clearance, export procedures, and arrival and presentation procedures when goods arrive at the external border of the EU. Each project in the MASP has a timeline, which is set between 2016 and 2025. The IT Strategy is based on a Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA), in line with the European Interoperability Framework (EIF) that recommends the development of a component-based service model allowing the establishment of European public services by reusing, as much as possible, existing service components²⁵. MASP is aimed at achieving important objectives:

- The creation of a coherent and interoperable electronic customs environment for the Community.
- Common understanding of the EU projects related to electronic customs and their dependencies.
- Coherence between these EU projects (business scope, IT technical strategies).
- Cooperation between all stakeholders (legal, business, IT, trade representatives at EU and national level).
- Implementation of the projects according to an agreed planning.

In 2016, the shift by customs to a paperless and fully electronic and interoperable environment was completed by adopting the Union Customs Code (UCC)²⁶. The UCC represents the new framework Regulation on the rules and procedures for customs throughout the EU.

In December 2022, after almost 10 years of pilot projects, the Regulation establishing the *EU Single Window Environment for Customs* was issued²⁷. This Regulation will enable interoperability between the customs and non-customs domains to streamline the electronic exchange of documents and information required for the goods clearance process. The framework legally establishes a centralised system to interconnect the import, export, and transit systems (see Table 1) of the Member States with Union non-customs systems that manage non-customs formalities. The system is known as the EU Customs Single Window Certificates Exchange System (EU CSW-CERTEX) and has been running in pilot mode since 2017. This system is designed to improve the sharing and processing of data submitted to customs and non-customs authorities by economic operators by ensuring that those authorities receive the original data in real time, see Figure 3. National customs authorities will be compliant with the data requirements specified in EU custom legislation by a technical tool, namely the EU Customs Data Model (EUCDM)²⁸. GEFEG.FX²⁹ is the design tool used for publishing the EUCDM model.

²¹ Electronic customs project: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/customs-4/electronic-customs_en

²² Custom Union: <https://unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/trans/doc/themes/UNDAC2C/Morocco2015/Saadaoui031215EN.pdf>

²³ MASP seminar: <https://www.fonasba.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/SAADAOUI-CUSTOMS-SINGLE-WINDOW.pdf>

²⁴ MASP: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/document/download/7d3e5929-8076-4ded-8ee5-9c380fb82115_en?filename=2019_masp_strategic_plan_en.pdf

²⁵ MASP service components: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2019-12/2019_masp_annex5_en.pdf

²⁶ UCC: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/union-customs-code-ucc-introduction_en

²⁷ EU Single Window Environment for Customs regulation: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2022/2399/oj>

²⁸ EUCDM: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/customs-4/union-customs-code/eu-customs-data-model-eucdm_en

²⁹ GEFEG.FX: <https://www.gefeg.com/en/gefeg-fx/>

The implementation of the EU Single Window Environment for Customs will be phased in gradually over the coming decade. The first phase will come into effect by 2025 and focus on enhancing intergovernmental exchanges at EU borders. Customs authorities will be able to automatically verify that non-customs formalities comply with the rules enforced by partner competent authorities. This verification will further ensure that the quantities of goods imported or exported at the EU level are properly monitored and controlled, thus reducing risks of fraud and gaps in the enforcement of non-customs requirements. The Union Customs Code, together with a new Multi-Annual-Strategic Plan for electronic customs (MASP-C) and the Work UCC Work Programme³⁰ set how the electronic systems should be implemented by approximately 2027.

Figure 2. Volume of international trade in 2022 (Source: EU Custom Union³¹)

Source: Unit R5, TAXUD, EC

Figure 3. Customs IT systems

³⁰ Work UCC Work Programme: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/customs-4/union-customs-code/ucc-work-programme_en

³¹ EU Custom Union: https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/customs-4/eu-customs-union-facts-and-figures/eu-customs-union-unique-world_en

Table 1. Customs IT Systems current portfolio (22 IT systems).

CENTRAL SYSTEMS	EU MOVEMENT SYSTEMS
ART2 (Activity Reporting Tool),	TTA (Transit Testing Application)
CN (Combined Nomenclature)	ECS (Export Control System)
COPIS (anti-COunterfeit and anti-PIracy System)	ICS (Import Control System)
CRMS (Customs Risk Management System)	
CS/MIS (Central Services/Management Information System)	
CS/RD (Central Services/Reference Data)	
DDS2 (Data Dissemination System)	
EBTI3 (European Binding Tariff Information)	
ECICS2 (European Customs Inventory of Chemical Substances)	
EOS (Economic Operator System)	
ISPP (Information System for Processing Procedures)	
Quota2 (Tariff quota management system)	
RSS (Regular Shipping Services)	
SMS (Specimen Management System)	
STTA (Standard Transit Test Application)	
Surv2 (Surveillance monitoring system)	
Susp (Tariff suspensions and autonomous quota)	
TARIC3 (Tarif intégré communautaire)	
TTA (Transit Testing Application)	

3. Collecting stakeholders' needs and requirements

According to a recent EUROSTAT report³², in 2020 there were more than 1.2 million enterprises in the transportation sector. This represents an increase of 2.3% compared with 2019, increase based mostly on the creation of new enterprises in the postal and courier activities sector. The transportation and storage services sector employed 10.3 million persons in 2020. The most significant number was registered in Spain, at more than two hundred thousand businesses. Besides Spain, four other EU member states were home to more than one hundred thousand transport businesses, namely Germany, France, Italy, and Poland.

So, logistic operators and enforcement authorities represent a complex network of stakeholders mutually involved in economic affairs and compliance checks. For this purpose, Sect. 3.1 is aimed at identifying and describing the characteristics of the main stakeholders identified by the KEYSTONE project. Sect. 3.2 describes the activities for creating a KEYSTONE stakeholders' register. Such a register is aimed at supporting any outreach and engagement activity that is requested from other tasks of the project (e.g., T1.2 and T1.3 need to investigate requirements, data and platforms used by the stakeholders, T3.2 needs to evaluate the UI/ UX of the KEYSTONE solution, etc.). Then, Sect. 3.3 provides details about the conversational survey that has been designed for collecting needs, requirements and expectations from the stakeholders involved in the cross-border logistics compliance checks on road transport operations.

The description of the stakeholders, the creation of a stakeholders' register and the results of the survey are aimed at supporting the activities included in the next tasks (T1.2, T1.3 in WP1, T2.1 in WP2, T3.2 in WP3, T6.2 in WP6).

3.1 KEYSTONE main stakeholders

Logistics refers to a subset of the “supply chain” activities. In particular, logistics refers to those activities related to the efficient management of the storage of products/goods, the organisation and execution of transport, and distribution to the end customer. In other words, the objective of logistics is to manage the order optimally. On the other hand, the objective of the supply chain is the comprehensive and global management of a product from its primary origin until it reaches the hands of the final recipient. The supply chain integrates more operations, apart from logistics, such as supply, manufacture and other types of activities related to the sales or marketing areas. So, logistic operators and enforcement authorities represent a complex network of stakeholders mutually involved in economic affairs and compliance checks.

According to the purpose and the objectives of KEYSTONE, three main categories of stakeholders have been identified: *logistic operators*, *freight terminals* and *enforcement authorities*. The survey described in Sect. 3.3 is addressed to these categories.

3.1.1 Logistic operators

A logistics network is part of a system designed to efficiently connect the production activities of a product and its consumption (sale to end customer). Its main purpose in the supply chain is transport and storage. Planning the logistics network is not a simple task because many variables must be considered: supply policy, volume of goods, transport systems, available warehouses and their racking configuration, future forecasts, etc. Some essential aspects must be considered for preparing a logistic plan: specify and classify what product the company markets and everything that this involves in the logistics plan, specify the logistics activity for each product, identify the transport needs of the product and its life cycle in the warehouse, storage

³² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Businesses_in_the_transportation_and_storage_sector#Structural_profile

capacity, the provision of warehouses or logistics centres, etc. The main objectives of the logistics network are here summarized:

- Reduction in transport, particularly in terms of frequency
- Reduction in handling
- Optimum stock level
- Reduction in the necessary checks

The main objective of the plan therefore is to simplify as much as possible the transport and storage processes so that they are quicker, simpler, more practical, and profitable using the number of human and mechanical resources strictly necessary. The demands and complexity of setting up the logistics network have led to many companies outsourcing these operations.

So, logistics operators are suppliers specialised in managing part or all the processes included in another company's supply chain, which can be storage, transport, distribution, or stock management itself. Companies that decide to contract logistics operators can avoid having to invest resources in developing their own logistics platform, in having to secure a transport fleet or in training personnel. Logistics operators are also responsible for the supervision, analysis, management and profitability of the phases of the supply chain assigned to them. Depending on the level of responsibility that the logistics operator has with the contracting company's supply chain, logistic operators can be divided into five different groups:

1. *first party logistics* also referred as 1PL (PL = Party Logistics), logistics operators are mainly the transportation companies in charge of transporting goods from one point to another.
2. 2PL, logistics operators are responsible for the transport and storage of the products.
3. 3PL, logistic operators are responsible for the total management of the storage and goods transport processes.
4. 4PL, logistic operators are responsible for supervising and coordinating the work of the 3PL.
5. 5PL, logistic operators are suppliers involved in the strategic and logistics planning of companies that contract their services.

According to the targets of the survey (see Sect. 3.3.1), in the "Logistic operators" category are also included "freight forwarders". In general, logistics operators have been playing the role of freight forwarding as they deal with consignments, cargo bookings, and safe delivery of goods. However, as more businesses are expanding their presence online, the difference is clearer. Supply chain management companies essentially deal with logistics, including transporting goods, warehousing, and dealing with legal aspects. At the same time, freight forwarders operate alone and are hired by such companies, playing the "interlink" part in the industry. Freight forwarders and logistics operators transport the goods using the same air, land, and water transport. Logistics have their fleet of vehicles, while the freight forwarders do not.

In this category, "shipping lines" are also taken into consideration. The key difference is that a freight shipping company is responsible of transporting goods between ports as well as getting them to the ports. Furthermore, a shipping line service is just port-to-port via sea travel rather than getting the goods to their destination.

3.1.2 Freight terminals

According to the definition³³ agreed between the European Union, the European Conference of Ministers of Transport (ECMT) and the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UN/ECE), a Combined transport (CT) is an "intermodal transport where the major part of the journey, in Europe, is by rail, inland waterways or sea, and any initial and/or final legs carried out by road are as short as possible". The combination of rail and road brings together the advantages of both rail and road: (i) rail can carry large quantities of freight over long distances, and (ii) road vehicles provide the flexibility needed for regional distribution.

³³ <https://www.uirr.com/en/road-rail-ct.html>

CT is the result of collaboration between different partners:

- The infrastructure managers (IMs), who put the railway network at the operators' disposal for a fee
- The railway undertakings (RUs), which operate rail traction services.
- The CT operators, who buy transport capacity from the RUs going from the equivalent of one isolated loading unit (distribution traffic) to the whole train.
- The terminal managers, who are, according to the circumstances, CT operators, RUs or local operators.
- The clients – road haulage companies, freight forwarders, logistics companies – who deliver the loading units to the departure terminal and collect them at the destination terminal.

CT operators market either terminal-to-terminal transports for logistics companies, freight forwarders and ship-owners, the initial and/or final legs by road being carried out by the clients, or the whole transport chain from the loader to the addressee. CT is recognised as being the most dynamic market for the transport of goods in Europe, which will most surely enable the RUs to participate in the growth of transport requirements essentially resulting from growing economic welfare and EU enlargement. Moreover, in comparison to road and maritime routings, road-rail CT makes it possible to limit the emission of pollutants and energy consumption. From the point of view of transport and environmental policy, the development of CT represents one of the main thrusts of the EU's and its Member States' strategy.

Intermodal terminals are key to access intermodal transport services and thus ensure efficient and road-competitive intermodal supply chains throughout Europe³⁴. Basic functions and additional services of CT terminals are given in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Functions and services of CT terminals

Information on intermodal terminals is required by intermodal operators, customers of intermodal transport services and the "interested community" of intermodal supporters. Several sources of information exist at:

- The intermodal terminal owners and operators themselves.
- Ports or logistics centres in which the terminals are located.
- Companies to whom the terminals belong.
- Regions or countries in which they are located.
- Intermodal operators or other institutions.

³⁴ <https://www.intermodal-terminals.eu/intermodal-terminals/>

Each of these sources provides a specific set of information in various formats. By the EU funded project (Marco Polo, 2009-2010)³⁵, the AGORA platform has been developed to provide a single access to uniform information on intermodal transport terminals in Europe, see Figure 5. The consortium was composed of intermodal terminal and intermodal transport operators from Austria, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, and The Netherlands.

Figure 5. AGORA platform, single access for intermodal transport terminals

DG MOVE has taken the initiative to set-up a common European web portal, the “Rail Facilities Portal (RFP)³⁶”, for information on all kinds of rail service facilities such as freight terminals, marshalling yards, maintenance facilities and fuelling stations. RFP shall offer service facility operators a comfortable opportunity to publish information about their facilities to comply with the relevant EU regulations and to promote their facilities and services. At the same time, shippers, rail operators and other rail logistics companies shall get a single source of information that allows them to identify relevant facilities for the planning and optimisation of their transport chains. In June 2020, RNE³⁷ (RailNetEurope) took over the ownership of the RFP from the European Commission. The operation / portal management of the RFP is carried out jointly by RNE and UIRR³⁸ (Union Internationale pour le transport combine Rail-Route). The aim of this cooperation is to involve not only service facilities operated by the members of RNE, but also all other service facilities in Europe.

3.1.3 Enforcement authorities

In general, a law enforcement agency or authority is any government agency responsible for the enforcement of the law. An enforcement authority might be geographically constrained in their ability to apply their powers: within a country, within a division of a country, or across a collection of countries, for example international organizations such as Interpol, or the European Union's Europol. Furthermore, different types of enforcement authorities exist: religious, internal affairs, police, military, etc. Many authorities have administrative and service responsibilities, often as their major responsibility, as well as their law enforcement responsibilities. This is typical of agencies such as customs or taxation agencies, which provide services and facilities to allow subjects to comply with relevant laws as their primary responsibilities.

Even restricting to the purpose of KEYSTONE, enforcement authorities have their own specificities, needs and requirements. Although the European Union issues laws that standardize the regulations within the entire perimeter of competence, each country can autonomously interpret and implement the rules. That obviously

³⁵ <https://www.intermodal-terminals.eu/agora-project/>

³⁶ Rail Facilities Portal: <https://railfacilitiesportal.eu/page/about>

³⁷ RNE: <https://rne.eu/>

³⁸ UIRR: <https://www.uirr.com/>

leads to an interoperability problem whenever the transport of goods involves crossing borders. Member States have established national registers and databases, some of which are interconnected and/or partially publicly accessible. Member States also have national risk rating systems which allow them to calculate the risk score of the undertaking based on the number and severity of infringements detected. The formula for the calculation of the risk score has been harmonised through Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/695. The purpose of the risk rating system is to help Member States identify non-compliant operators and target them with more frequent and comprehensive checks. Despite developments made at national, European, and international levels to step up enforcement by introducing electronic registers, electronic documents, communication systems, controlling compliance with the complexity of the rules applicable to highly mobile road transport sector remains a huge challenge. The enforcement system is broadly conceived (including by the enforcement community) as ineffective, inefficient, inconsistent, burdensome, and costly. Carriers and drivers lose money and business opportunities due to lengthy, random, and unnecessary controls while enforcement authorities are facing insufficient human, financial and technical resources to effectively control compliance with the complex framework of the rules.

The increasing internationalisation of road transport operations and enhancing complexity of the road transport rules make enforcement more than ever dependent on administrative cooperation between national authorities, mutual assistance and the exchange of information and data about operators, drivers, vehicles, and goods transported. To facilitate this cooperation for cross-border enforcement, the EU has developed several IT systems allowing for secure Authority-to-Authority (A2A) communication and transfer of data. The most relevant systems and their functions are presented in Table 1.

Table 2. Main IT systems for the implementation of the EU road transport legislation

IT System	Function
TACHOnet ³⁹	Electronic exchange of information between MS to combat fraud on the possession of driver (tachograph) cards. Legal base: Regulation (EU) 2016/68
ERRU ⁴⁰	Electronic exchange of information between MS on the transport undertakings allowing to check good repute, community license, number plates of vehicles (future), risk score (future) and to notify the result of roadside checks (infringements, clean checks). Legal base: Regulation (EU) 2016/480
RESPER ⁴¹	Electronic exchange of information between MS to combat fraud on driving licences. Legal base: Directive (EU) 2015/413
IMI ⁴²	Internal Market Information system - secure, multilingual online tool that facilitates the exchange of information between MS to check compliance with the rules on posting of drivers, to combat letterbox companies and to exchange information on application of driving and rest time rules. Legal base: Directive (EU) 2020/1057
eFTI ⁴³	The eFTI environment composed of eFTI platforms hosting the electronic freight transport information, and authorities' systems allowing access to the regulatory information concerning a freight transport operation on eFTI platforms via a unique electronic identifying link. Legal base: Regulation (EU) 2020/1056

Nevertheless, these platforms have some limitations. They do not always guarantee accessibility, compatibility, and exchange of data in a safe and reliable way. As a result, these systems often fail to provide substantial efficiency gains and relief for authorities and logistic operators. To be more concrete, the methodologies and technologies currently adopted by the authorities lack interoperability and flexibility to face the future challenges of the logistics sector. Despite the introduction of electronic registers and electronic documents most information is still available in the form of paper documents (e.g., driving license). It is

³⁹ TACHOnet: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/road/tachograph/tachonet_en

⁴⁰ ERRU: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-modes/road/rules-governing-access-profession/european-register-road-transport-undertakings-erru_en

⁴¹ RESPER: <https://road-safety.transport.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2021-07/resper.pdf>

⁴² IMI: https://ec.europa.eu/internal_market/imi-net/index_en.htm

⁴³ eFTI: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/summary/electronic-freight-transport-information.html>

estimated that 99% of cross-border transport operations in Europe require that at least one delivery note (CMR⁴⁴) in paper format is still used along the route and across the European countries. This means that only 1% of freight operations are served by a fully digital exchange of information.

Moreover, a difficult access to complete and reliable data on drivers, operators, vehicles, and goods heavily affects the operational activity of enforcement authorities. Due to the lack of contextual data, a risk assessment about the technical condition of the vehicle, the driver's non-compliant behaviour or the operator's high-risk score cannot be performed in advance. In this scenario, only a fraction of vehicles on the road are checked and many of them are randomly stopped for roadside checks. So, the risk is that serious offenders might avoid the necessary and fundamental checks. In conclusion, due to the complexity of the rules applicable to the mobility and to the transport sector, the monitoring of compliance checks remains a big challenge.

In conclusion, platforms described in Table 2 are not linked to each other. They must be consulted separately to gain a holistic picture. Each platform offers distinct user-experience and has a learning curve. Further smart enforcement systems should be investigated and developed. Two models of smart enforcement are being assessed: (i) a centralized model: providing a single access point to enforcers to connect to different information exchange systems, and (ii) a decentralized model: allowing enforcers to gain access to all relevant data relating to driver, vehicle, operator, and cargo via cloud-based infrastructure. The eFTI framework (see Sect. 2.2.2) could present opportunities to standardize/harmonize data sharing.

3.2 KEYSTONE stakeholders' register

This section describes the activities for creating the KEYSTONE stakeholders' register in compliance with GDPR rules. Such a register is aimed at supporting any outreach and engagement activity that is requested from other tasks of the project (e.g., T1.2 and T1.3 need to investigate requirements, data and platforms used by the stakeholders, T3.2 needs to evaluate the UI/ UX of the KEYSTONE solution, etc.).

According to the purpose and the objectives of KEYSTONE, the register contains contacts belonging to three main categories of stakeholders: *logistic operators*, *freight terminals* and *enforcement authorities* (see Sect. 3.1). To create a GDPR compliant register of stakeholders, a simple Microsoft form has been prepared, see Figure 6. The form requests the following information:

- Name and surname
- Email address
- Name of the organization
- Website link of the organisation (optional)
- Type of the organization

⁴⁴ CMR: https://unece.org/DAM/trans/conventn/cmr_e.pdf

Contact information collection form

Sezione 1

You are invited to be included in a newsletter and/or in a stakeholders register for participating to the activities of KEYSTONE research project (<https://www.keystone-project.com/>). KEYSTONE project has received funding from the Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101103740.

The overarching goal is the development and conceptualization of a sustainable, efficient, and safe transport system, which allows enforcement authorities to access data for compliance checks.

Please, provide the following information:

1. Your name and surname *

Figure 6: A snapshot of the MS Forms for the KEYSTONE stakeholders' register

Further, in compliance with GDPR rules, the participants can provide explicit consent to receive the KEYSTONE newsletter and/or explicit consent to participate in consultation and coaching activities within the KEYSTONE project. At this purpose, an ad-hoc privacy policy has been prepared with the support of a law consultant, see Annex 1.

Once it has been finalized, the form has been delivered to two different groups of people:

1. "internal" to the consortium. Each KEYSTONE partner has shared on an Excel file those contacts deemed potentially interested in the project (around 280 people).
2. "external" to the consortium. Some members of logistics associations and organizations worldwide and in Europe⁴⁵ (e.g., FIATA⁴⁶, UIRR⁴⁷, FEDESPEDI⁴⁸, ESPO⁴⁹, IIFA⁵⁰, etc.) have been identified (around two thousand contacts). More details about the distribution of the form and of the survey are given in Sect. 3.3.5.

The form has been promoted via:

- The KEYSTONE website⁵¹.
- The survey (see Sect. 3.3). At the end of the survey, a link to the form was accessible for those interested in being included in the KEYSTONE register.
- The LinkedIn webpage⁵² of KEYSTONE.

At the time of submitting this deliverable, the KEYSTONE stakeholders' register includes 15 contacts who will be updated and engaged throughout the project (May 2026). This activity refers to the task T6.2 (WP6) that starts at M6 and ends at M35. Contextually, the form will be distributed and promoted for the entire project duration (M35) to collect more people and enhance the impact on the activities.

⁴⁵ List of Logistic Associations <https://www.scmo.net/logistics-associations>

⁴⁶ FIATA: <https://fiata.org/>

⁴⁷ UIRR: <https://www.uirr.com/>

⁴⁸ FEDESPEDI: <https://www.fedespedi.it/>

⁴⁹ ESPO: <https://www.espo.be/>

⁵⁰ IIFA: <https://www.iifa.ie/>

⁵¹ KEYSTONE website: <https://www.keystone-project.com/>

⁵² KEYSTONE LinkedIn page: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/keystone-eu/about/>

3.3 KEYSTONE survey

The survey is aimed at collecting needs, requirements, and expectations of a minimum of 300 targeted stakeholders including different types of institutions (such as the EC, national, regional, and local authorities) and industry players (e.g., retailers, suppliers, logistic operators, freight terminals, etc.). The main goal is to identify relevant needs and obstacles that currently affect the controls performed by enforcement authorities on road cross-border logistics. In particular, the survey aims to investigate which kind of data are actually shared with enforcement authorities and between actors involved in the transport operations (e.g. logistic operators, transport companies, freight terminals, etc...), which tools are used to exchange data and the current integration of national platforms with the European platforms (e.g. ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI, eFTI platforms, etc...), which has been designed to facilitate cross-border compliance checks. Furthermore, the survey aims to investigate the role of the digital transformation in enhancing the controls. As T1.1 is the first task of the KEYSTONE project, the survey aims to start raising awareness about the vision and the objectives of the project. At this purpose, the survey includes the link to the form (see Sect. 3.2) for exploring the availability of stakeholders to actively support the KEYSTONE activities.

To facilitate the compilation of responses to the survey and increase the number of potential respondents, the survey has been designed as a totally anonymous tool. No personal information is collected by the survey and the results are analysed in an aggregated form with the goal of gathering the general overview of the compliance checks in the logistic sector. As the number of stakeholders is huge (according to a recent EUROSTAT report⁵³, in 2020 there were almost 1.2 million transportation enterprises), the number of respondents to the survey will likely represent a small sample of the population of interest. So, the survey is not aimed at providing a statistical significance, namely quantifying whether a result is likely due to chance or not. Notwithstanding, the analysis of the results will be able to point out what, in terms of controls, are the main needs and barriers that the stakeholders are facing daily with. Such an information will support and guide further investigations (see T1.2, T1.3 of WP1).

3.3.1 Targets

The survey is aimed at collecting needs and requirements from a sample of all stakeholders who are involved in the field of cross-border logistics compliance checks. To this purpose, the survey is addressed to three target groups:

1. *Logistic operators*: logistic operators, transport companies, freight forwarders, shipping lines, as described in Sect. 3.1.1.
2. *Freight terminals*: freight terminals which manage multimodal transports (road, rail, air, sea transports), as described in Sect. 3.1.2.
3. *Enforcement authorities*: road police, customs, finance police, ministry, public authorities (e.g., seaport authorities), as described in Sect. 3.1.3.

Given the complexity of the ecosystem of stakeholders and EU regulations in the transportation sector, the survey is also open to any expert (e.g., academic professor, senior consultant) who can support the business analysis.

3.3.2 Structure

The survey aims to collect needs and obstacles experienced from three target groups (see Sect. 3.3.1) who operate in the cross-border logistic sector. The survey has been designed as anonymous and branching into

⁵³ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Businesses_in_the_transportation_and_storage_sector#Structural_profile

three different flows of questions (sub-surveys). The content of each branch was customized according to the specific target group the survey was addressed to. After a joint introduction about the KEYSTONE project, the survey forks in three different branches in which the questions and messages are customized according to the target group. So, basically, respondents can fill out the survey by selecting the branch with which they identify most.

The three branches (and the questions included) are parallel and separated. They end up with the same question, namely the opportunity to provide explicit consent to be included in the KEYSTONE register, see Sect. 3.2. The three branches deal with almost the same topics, but the questions and messages are customized according to the specific respondent's category. The survey aims to investigate the aspects to be considered for improving compliance checks, digital tools used (both at national and European levels), data already shared among authorities and logistic actors (logistic operators, transport companies and freight terminals) and data, not currently shared, that might help optimizing logistic processes.

In particular, the branches of “*Logistic operators*” and “*Freight terminals*” investigate the following topics:

- *Profiling*: generic characteristics (no sensitive data) of the respondents, such as the country and the type of transport managed (international, air/road/rail/sea transport, etc.).
- *Data and technology role*: information to be considered for improving the checks and the role of digital transformation from the perspective of who is subject to compliance checks.
- *Data sharing with*:
 - *enforcement authorities*: the type of data shared with authorities and the digital platforms used.
 - *other actors*: the type of data shared with other logistic operators/freight terminals and the digital platforms used.
- *Data needs*: data not actually shared that might be useful to improve productivity and efficiency.
- *EU platform*: experience with the exchange of information with the EU platform (e.g., ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI, eFTI platforms, etc..) and, in case, feedback on them (improvements, integration with national platforms, etc...)

The questions of the branch for “*Enforcement authority*” are about:

- *Profiling*: generic characteristics (no sensitive data) of the respondents, such as the country, the category of authority and the rules enforced.
- *Data and technology role*: information to be considered and the role of digital transformation in improving compliance checks from the perspective of who performs compliance checks.
- *Data needs*: data not actually shared by the stakeholders (e.g., logistic operators, freight terminals, etc...) that might be helpful for improving checks.
- *Digital platforms*:
 - *Current platforms*: digital platform currently used for carrying out controls and possible improvements.
 - *EU platform*: the survey investigates if the respondents currently used the EU platform (ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI, eFTI platforms, etc..) and, in case, they opinion on them (improvements, issues ...)

The content and the questions have been collaboratively designed and validated by Cefriel and by the partners CIM, Gruber and COORTE which represent respectively the categories of freight terminals, logistic operators, and enforcement authorities. T-Bridge have been supporting the formulation of questions related to data exchanged and digital platforms currently used by the stakeholders (as requested in T1.3).

3.3.3 Multiple languages

To facilitate the distribution around all European countries, the survey has been defined in multiple languages. The survey has been translated from the original English version into other 5 different languages: Italian, Spanish, French, German, and Greek. A multiple-language survey aims to facilitate the compilation of the survey (acceptance rate) and to increase the number of potential respondents (response rate). The full list of questions is fully reported in Annex 1 (English version).

3.3.4 Conversational (Coney)

To make it more effective and intuitive, the survey has been designed as “conversational” allowing users to share their feedback more quickly and enjoyably. To this purpose, the designing and the implementation of the survey have been done with the Coney toolkit (Celino & Re Calegari, 2020), a tool developed by Cefriel (<https://www.cefrirel.com/coney-toolkit/>) for administering questionnaires in a chat form. While engaged in filling out the survey, respondents can experience the filling out process like a conversation with another person rather than a pure list of questions. Coney supports the survey designer in all the phases of the data collection, from the design and implementation of the survey up to the administration and the analysis of results. In a conversational survey, the questions are formulated in a colloquial form and connected in a conversational flow to improve the compilation experience. The creation of a storytelling, as a conversation between two persons, helps to create a context and let the respondents think about different topics in a guided way. Figure 7 shows the chat-based interface of Coney.

Figure 7. The interface of the conversational survey with Coney

3.3.5 Distribution & promotion

To have a survey anonymous by design, the survey has been published by a unique link (URL). The same link, generated by the Coney tool (see Sect. 3.3.4), has been (and will) distributed to all participants. A compilation period of two months has been planned: from the 13th of September to the 14th of November 2023. During the compilation period, a weekly update was sent to partners in charge of the dissemination, reporting some aggregated statistics, to monitor and in case push for further dissemination actions. The survey has been promoted by several channels:

- *email* sent to stakeholders

- *news* published on the websites ofc KEYSTONE and Cefriel. A dedicated page⁵⁴ for presenting the questionnaire and some news⁵⁵ for promoting the launch of the survey were created. An article was also published on the Cefriel website⁵⁶
- *posts* published on social media, mainly LinkedIn⁵⁷ and X⁵⁸. 10+ posts/tweets were published from the official account of KEYSTONE and reposted by the partners
- *a press releases* and an *article*⁵⁹ published on magazines
- *conferences* (e.g., STA conference held in Milan on 26th October 2023)

To share the link of the survey via email, a list of potential stakeholders/respondents has been identified. This list contains representatives of all the three target groups identified: logistic/transport organizations and companies, associations, experts, ministry, authorities, etc. The list of potential respondents was created by collecting contacts from different sources:

- the network of contacts shared from KEYSTONE's partners (about 300 contacts)
- the list of members published on the web and belonging to EU/international organizations & associations (e.g., FIATA) (about 500 contacts)
- commercial databases (i.e., CreditSafe) containing the contacts of Italian companies with revenue larger than three million euros. (about 1200 contacts)

The number of contacts included in the list is higher than the KPI of 300 compilation to face the problem of low response rate in surveys. According to GDPR rules, once the link of the survey has been shared via email, the list of potential stakeholders has been deleted.

3.4 KEYSTONE survey analysis

This section describes the analysis of the answers provided by the participants to the survey. The analysis refers to the answers collected in the last two months, namely 13th of September - 14th of November 2023. The analysis aims to collect relevant needs and obstacles that currently affect the controls performed by enforcement authorities on road cross-border logistics. To facilitate the interpretation of the results, each category of stakeholders has been analysed separately. The survey is still open and further data will be collected until April (or May) 2024 to achieve at least 300 respondents. The analysis of the answers collected in the period 15th of November - 16th of April (May) 2023 will be included in the deliverable D1.2.

3.4.1 General statistics

The survey has been filled out by 203 respondents. 91 of them have completed the survey (45% completion rate), with a median completion time of 5 minutes and 30 seconds. The distribution of completed answers collected per day is reported in Figure 8. A burst in the compilation process is present at the end of September (beginning of October). In general, the process of filling out the survey is quite “flat”.

⁵⁴ Survey dedicated page on KEYSTONE website: <https://www.keystone-project.com/stakeholder-survey>

⁵⁵ News about the survey launch on KEYSTONE website: <https://www.keystone-project.com/news/stakeholder-community-survey-launch>

⁵⁶ News on Cefriel website: <https://www.cefril.com/news-en/keystone-project-digital-technologies-simplify-compliance-checks-for-cross-border-transportation/?lang=en>

⁵⁷ LinkedIn KEYSTONE account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/keystone-eu/>

⁵⁸ X KEYSTONE account: https://twitter.com/KEYSTONE_EU

⁵⁹ Article published on AgendaDigitale: <https://www.agendadigitale.eu/mercati-digitali/una-logistica-piu-efficiente-con-autorita-esecutive-smart-le-iniziativa-ue/>

Figure 8. Number of compilations per day

As the survey is available in multiple languages, information on the specific language used from the participants for filling out the survey has been collected: 35% of respondents filled the survey in English, 30% in Spanish, 27% in Italian and the remaining 8% in German, Greek and French.

Table 3 shows the number of compilations started and completed for each target group. The completion rate is around 50%.

Table 3. Number of respondents for each target group

Target group	N° of started compilations	N° of completed compilation	Completion rate (N°completed/N°started)
Logistic operators	108	58	54%
Freight terminals	12	7	58%
Enforcement authorities	51	26	51%

The analysis of the points of leaving of unfinished surveys shows that the 25% of unfinished compilations (28 out of 112) ended at the very beginning of the questionnaire, where the belonging category was asked (i.e., logistic operator, freight terminal or enforcement authority). This may indicate that the activity of survey promotion and dissemination also reached out to some people outside the target, who rightly left the compilation.

Other points of leaving are just after the branches in the three categories, during the profiling questions and when the survey starts introducing the core topics of the questionnaire (role of data and technology in enhancing controls). Here, in all the three branches, at least 50% of respondents abandoned the compilation. In other words, most of the unfinished compilations ended at the very beginning of the survey. The abandonment rate (roughly 50%) is mainly due to the difficulty to answer the pivotal questions that KEYSTONE is going to investigate, namely what the needs in terms of data and technologies are.

To ensure high quality data and the opportunity to identify, gather and properly interpret the needs and requirements of the participants, the analysis described in the following sections only refers to those surveys that have been completed, namely 91.

3.4.2 Results of “Logistic operators” group

This section describes the analysis of the answers provided by stakeholders belonging to the category “Logistic operators” (see Sect. 3.1.1).

3.4.2.1 Profiling

The analysis is based on 58 answers collected from logistic operators, transport companies and users located in 13 different European countries (Spain, Italy, Slovakia, Romania, Netherlands, Greece, Germany, Finland, Estonia, Denmark, Belgium, United Kingdom, and Austria), as shown in Figure 10. Most of the answers (74%) were collected from logistic operators, transport companies and users who have their headquarters in Spain, Italy, and Belgium, as described in Table 4.

50% of respondents carry out international transport, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Logistic operators: international transport.

Figure 10. Logistic operators: map of countries of headquarters.

Table 4. Logistic operators: number of responses per country.

Country	Num. logistic operators
Spain	21
Italy	13
Belgium	9
Netherlands	3
Austria	2
Greece	2
Denmark	1
Estonia	1
Finland	1
Germany	1
Romania	1
Slovakia	1
United Kingdom	1
Other country	1

3.4.2.2 Data and technology role

76% of respondents agree that data and technology play a pivotal role in improving and enhancing compliance checks carried out by enforcement authorities, optimizing logistics processes and transport sustainability, as shown in Figure 11.

The remaining 24% believes that digital transformation is important but other aspects should be properly considered. The legislation should be simplified, the definition of regulation should be improved as well as the harmonization and the cooperation between member states. Other aspects to be considered are the geo-political context (e.g., non-EU borders, Brexit, uncertainty of regulations), the language barriers, the specific type of shipping (dangerous or perishable goods, project cargo) and the technical preparation of the staff and operators.

Figure 11. Logistic operators: role of data and technology in enhancing controls.

3.4.2.3 Data sharing with enforcement authorities

60% of respondents declare to share data with enforcement authorities and among them the 18% shares data with all the authorities, as shown in Figure 12. The other 42% share data only with some authorities, mainly with customs and port authorities, as shown in Figure 13.

Do you currently share your data with enforcement authorities?

Figure 12. Logistic operators: data sharing with enforcement authorities.

If you share data only with some authorities, with which ones?

Figure 13. Logistic operators: main authorities involved in data sharing.

The 40% of logistic operators who do not share data with the authorities declared that this is not only due to a lack of technologies. In many countries data cannot be shared electronically and the documentation to be shared may contain critical information about the company and their clients. Therefore, without legal securities a general sharing of data may be problematic.

Other respondents do not share data because it is not mandatory, and they send data only when it is explicitly requested for legal inspections. Furthermore, respondents are not encouraged to share data because they declare to have neither benefits nor income.

As shown in Figure 14, the main kind of data shared with authorities are about:

- Cargo (e.g., types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Vehicle (e.g., technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Operation (e.g., type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular)
- Driver (e.g., professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times)

Figure 14. Logistic operators: types of data shared with enforcement authorities.

As concern the digital platforms used for sharing data with the authorities, a variety of tools is used for data sharing. Some operators use simple digital solutions such as *email* and *MS Excel*, because many cities or countries are not ready for the shift to standardized solutions.

Other operators use *own developed software* or software provided by company like *NovaSystem*⁶⁰ and *Descartes*⁶¹. Platforms defined by *enforcement authorities, maritime, railway and airline companies* are also adopted. Examples of digital tools provided by the Italian Customs and Monopolies Agency (*ADM*)⁶² are the *Digital Customs Service E.D.I.*⁶³ and *Intrastat*⁶⁴. Other logistic operators declare to use the *NAP (National Access Point)*⁶⁵ and to adopt the *GTFS*⁶⁶ standard to make public transit data universally accessible.

⁶⁰ NovaSystem: <https://www.novasystems.it/eng/home.html>

⁶¹ Descartes: <https://www.descartes.com/home>

⁶² ADM: <https://www.adm.gov.it/portale/en/home>

⁶³ E.D.I.: <https://www.adm.gov.it/portale/en/dogane/operatore/servizi-online/servizio-telematico-doganale-e.d.i.>

⁶⁴ Intrastat: <https://www.adm.gov.it/portale/en/dogane/operatore/servizi-online/intrastat>

⁶⁵ NAP: https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/intelligent-transport-systems/road/action-plan-and-directive/national-access-points_en

⁶⁶ GTFS: <https://gtfs.org/>

3.4.2.4 Data sharing with other actors

50% of respondents declare to share data with other actors (e.g., other logistic operators, freight terminal operators, public authorities, etc.), and half of them exchange information automatically by digital and integrated platforms, as shown in Figure 15.

20% of respondents do not share data but they are interested in exploring this chance. They do not currently share data because they have neither income nor benefits, and they want to keep market advantages. In addition, the lack of an appropriate digital system limits data sharing.

The remaining 30% declare to be not interested in sharing data, due to confidentiality and competition reasons.

Figure 15. Logistic operators: sharing data with other actors.

Different types of data are shared with other actors, as shown in Figure 16. The main are:

- Cargo (e.g., types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Vehicle (e.g., technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Driver (e.g., professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times)

Figure 16. Logistic operators: types of data shared with other actors.

The main digital platforms used for data sharing are platforms owned by the company to which the access to suppliers is given or open data sharing platforms such as BRUcloud⁶⁷.

⁶⁷ BRUcloud: <https://brucloud.com/>

3.4.2.5 Data needs

57% of respondents declare that some data, not currently shared with them, may be useful for improving their productivity and efficiency.

The types of data needed are about road traffic and accidents on the road, closed roads and planned road closures, waiting times at border crossing, delays of train and ships, notification of bad weather conditions on the road, occupation of a parking area, height limits, drivers, and the vehicles.

Figure 17. Logistic operators: data currently not shared that might be helpful.

3.4.2.6 EU platforms

This survey is aimed at collecting the feedback on some European platforms that are designed to facilitate the cooperation for cross-border enforcement. In particular, the analysis is focused on the ERRU, IMI, TACHOnet, Resper and eFTI platforms.

Figure 18 shows that only the 17% of respondents have exchanged information with these platforms and the most used platforms are IMI and eFTI platforms, as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 18. Logistic operators: information exchange with EU platforms.

Figure 19. Logistic operators: EU platform used.

These EU platforms are integrated with the national platform only in half of these cases. Respondents who do not have their system integrated think that this integration could help reduce the administrative burden and the main issue is related to the harmonization of data formats and interfaces.

3.4.3 Results of “Freight terminals” group

This section describes the analysis of the answers provided by stakeholders belonging to the category “Freight terminals” (see Sect. 3.1.1).

3.4.3.1 Profiling

The analysis is based on 7 answers collected from 7 freight terminals, 5 located in Italy, 1 in Greece and 1 in Spain, as shown in Figure 20 and detailed in Table 5.

Table 5. Freight terminals: number of responses per country

Country	Num. terminals
Italy	5
Greece	1
Spain	1

Figure 20. Freight terminals: map of countries of headquarters.

Most of the terminals (86%) carries out international transport, as shown in Figure 21. The multimodal transports performed are road-air, road-rail, road-sea, and road-rail-sea, as shown in Table 5.

Table 6. Freight terminals: type of multimodal transport.

Multimodal transport	Num. terminals
Road + air	2
Road + rail	1
Road + sea	1
Road + rail + sea	1
Air	1
Road	1

Figure 21. Freight terminals: international transport.

3.4.3.2 Data and technology role

All the respondents agree that data and technology play a pivotal role in improving and enhancing compliance checks carried out by enforcement authorities, optimizing logistics processes and transport sustainability.

Figure 22. Freight terminals: role of data and technology in enhancing controls.

3.4.3.3 Data sharing with enforcement authorities

57% of respondents (4 out of 7) declare to share data with enforcement authorities, as shown in Figure 23.

The main reason for not sharing data with authorities is that there are no tools suitable for sharing data.

Do you currently share your data with enforcement authorities?

Figure 23. Freight terminals: data sharing with enforcement authorities.

As Figure 24 shows, the main kind of data shared with authorities are about:

- Cargo (e.g. types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Vehicle (e.g. technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Operation (e.g., type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular)
- Operator (e.g., authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good repute, risk score)
- Transport status forecast and actual data (e.g. train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep)

Figure 24. Freight terminals: types of data shared with enforcement authorities.

The main digital platforms used for sharing data with the authorities are Port Community Systems and other systems related to freight terminals.

3.4.3.4 Data sharing with other actors

71% of respondents (5 out of 7) declare to share data with other actors (e.g., logistic operators, other freight terminal operators, public authorities, etc.), and 4 of them exchange information automatically by digital and integrated platforms, as shown in Figure 25. One of the reasons for not sharing data is the lack of specific platforms to exchange information.

Figure 25. Freight terminals: data sharing with other actors.

Figure 26 shows the main types of data shared with other actors. They are:

- Cargo (e.g., types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing)
- Vehicle (e.g., technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections)
- Transport status forecast and actual data (e.g., train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep)
- Operation (e.g., type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular)

Figure 26. Freight terminals: types of data shared with other actors.

The main digital tools used for sharing data with other actors are the Port Community Systems, the digital ecosystem of the freight terminal and the sending of EDI messages (Electronic Data Interchange) to other terminals or railways companies.

3.4.3.5 Data needs

71% of respondents (5 out of 7) declare that some data, not currently shared with them, may be useful for improving their productivity and efficiency, as shown in Figure 27

The types of data needed are customs data, estimated time of arrival (ETA), estimated time for loading and unloading, delays, cargo volume, types of transported goods, shipments and all the data that could help in organizing checks involving different types of authorities.

Figure 27. Freight terminals: data currently not shared that might be helpful.

3.4.3.6 EU platforms

None of the respondents has never exchanged information with the European platform designed to facilitate cross-border compliance checks and analysed in this survey (ERRU, IMI, TACHOnet, Resper and eFTI platforms).

3.4.4 Results of “Enforcement authorities” group

This section describes the analysis of the answers provided by stakeholders belonging to the category “Enforcement authorities” (see Sect. 3.1.1).

3.4.4.1 Profiling

The analysis is based on 26 answers collected from 26 enforcement authorities located in 13 different European countries (Croatia, Cyprus, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Netherlands, Romania,

Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom), as shown in Figure 28. The number of answers collected for each country is reported in Table 7.

Figure 28. Enforcement authorities: map of countries of headquarters.

Table 7. Enforcement authorities: number of responses per country.

Country	Num. authorities
Spain	6
Italy	4
Slovenia	3
Ireland	2
Netherlands	2
Romania	2
Croatia	1
Cyprus	1
Hungary	1
Lithuania	1
Malta	1
Sweden	1
United Kingdom	1

As regards the category of authorities, answers are collected from ministries, customs, public authorities (e.g., seaport authority) and road police. Further answers have been collected from other authorities that do not identify themselves in the category predefined in the survey (category “Other”). Table 8 shows the number of compilations was collected for each category of authorities and the countries where they are located.

Table 8. Enforcement authorities: responses collected per authority type and corresponding countries.

Authority type	Num. answers	Countries
Ministry	11	Spain, Romania, Slovenia, United Kingdom, Netherlands, Hungary, Cyprus, Croatia
Public authority (e.g. sea port authority)	7	Sweden, Spain, Malta, Italy, Ireland
Customs	3	Italy, Slovenia
Other	3	Spain, Italy
Road police	2	Spain, Lithuania

The main rules enforced by respondents are driving/rest times, cabotage, ADR, posting of workers, roadworthiness, weights, and dimensions, as shown in Figure 29.

Figure 29. Enforcement authorities: rules enforced.

3.4.4.2 Data and technology role

88% of respondents agree that data and technology play a pivotal role in improving and enhancing compliance checks.

Only a few respondents think that there are other aspects to be considered, in particular administrative and organizational aspects.

Figure 30. Enforcement authorities: role of data and technology in enhancing controls.

3.4.4.3 Data needs

85% of respondents declare that there are some data, currently not shared with them, that might be provided by the stakeholders (e.g., logistic operators, terminal/freight operators, authorities of other countries, etc.) and that might improve the checks, as shown in Figure 31.

Some respondents would like to exchange vehicles information and status such as data about the last RSI (Road Side Inspection) and PTI (Periodical Technical Inspection). This data could help avoid the same truck being checked in RSI several times during the same trip and it could also be a step towards mutual recognition of PTI results.

A centralized, European-wide database like the one implemented for Certificate of Conformity (COC) might be also a good solution to implement.

Figure 31. Enforcement authorities: data currently not shared that might be helpful.

Other respondents think that it would be important to have more data to combat and bottom out fraud related offences in a more efficient way. The desired data is anything that could help the officers prove beyond doubt the route a vehicle took up to the point of inspection (traffic data, shipping manifests, tolling data, etc...). For example, GPS vehicle tracking could be used to verify the actual data from tachograph and to exclude manipulations. The sharing of the shipping manifests, which includes information about the people on the incoming ferries, could help profiling the incoming operators and target high risk ones.

Other data useful for improving checks are about loads, timesheets, mileages or driven kilometres, shipping order forms, weighing-in documents, accurate traffic information and roadblocks, Expected Time Arrival (ETA), origin-destination data, waiting times in terminals, number of subcontracting and transportation price.

The data sharing across European countries is another aspect highlighted by respondents. They would like to have real time sharing of driving license data and operator licensing, as well as data about bad practices in transportation in each country and documents, regulations, control and inspection procedures or protocols specific for each country. Data about drivers and transport company documentation should be exchanged between Member States by the ERRU system, but currently some States (e.g., Portugal) do not use this application for sharing data. The way in which data is shared among Member States should be compliant with regulation EU 2020/1056 (eFTI).

3.4.4.4 Current platforms

The main platforms used for carrying out controls and compliance checks include the Port Community Systems, IT systems provided by the national ministry, the national customs agency (*STD – Sistema Telematico Doganale*⁶⁸), the police systems, the card issuing authority and the licensing authority.

DBs and software developed internally are also used; some of them are also linked to databases of EU platforms such as TACHOnet.

⁶⁸ <https://telematico.adm.gov.it/TelematicoFunzioniDiAccessoWEBNG/FunzioniDiAccessoServlet?UC=10/SC=1/ST=1>

Some commercial platforms used are TachoScan Control⁶⁹ (for checks of drivers' working time) and AETRControl⁷⁰ (a professional tachograph evaluator for checking driving and resting times).

85% of respondents think that these platforms should be improved and enhanced, mainly by integrating new data sources, as shown in Figure 32.

Respondents would like to have Europe wide transport data in real time for instant checks. This means having for example the same data on out-of-state vehicles and drivers as they have for their own and accessible at the roadside, (i.e., tachograph card data, CPC card data, driver licensing data, vehicle roadworthiness data etc..).

Figure 32. Enforcement authorities: national platforms improvements required.

In addition, other relevant integration could be data about inspection carried out on operators based on EU Common risk rating formula, authorizations and infringements in other states, On-Board Diagnostic (OBD) data, data from satellite tracking, toll cost, data about loads (quantity of loads, place of delivery, route of transport, number of passengers traveling aboard, tachograph data, driver data such as qualification), transport company data and data about rail transport.

Integration with data shared via European platforms is also needed, for example ERRU community licenses data and data related to eFTI regulations.

3.4.4.5 EU platforms

To facilitate the cooperation for cross-border enforcement, the EU has developed several IT systems allowing for secure communication and transfer of data. ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI and eFTI platforms are analysed in this survey.

69% of respondents declare to use one or more of these platforms for carrying out controls, as shown in Figure 33. The 23% do not even know these platforms and the 8% do not use them even though they know them.

The most used EU platforms are TACHOnet, IMI and ERRU, as shown in Figure 34. TACHOnet is used by almost all respondents and IMI by the 89%. Resper and the eFTI platforms are used by less than the 10% of respondents.

⁶⁹ <https://tachoscancontrol.com/en/home/>

⁷⁰ <https://www.aetrcontrol.eu/>

Do you use one (or more) of the EU platforms for carrying out your checks regarding international transportation?

Figure 33. Enforcement authorities: rate of adoption of EU platforms.

Figure 34. Enforcement authorities: EU platforms used.

Respondents who declared to use at least one of these EU platforms think that the best way for improving them is by integrating the different EU platforms and making them accessible by a single interface. Other aspects to be enhanced are the EU platforms' accessibility (especially for roadside checks) and the data currently provided by the platforms, as shown in Figure 35.

According to your experience, how these platforms should be improved and enhanced?

Figure 35. Enforcement authorities: suggested improvements to EU platforms.

4. Conclusions

This document represents the Deliverable 1.1 “Stakeholders’ identification and needs” (D1.1). It is the final output of T1.1, “Stakeholders’ definition, needs and board implementation” that is part of WP1, “Gap Analysis and State of the Art”. D1.1 provides an overview about the most relevant projects related to a “smart enforcement for road transport”, the creation of the KEYSTONE stakeholders’ register, and the analysis of the KEYSTONE survey.

Under Horizon Europe Framework several projects have been funded to develop systems for accessing real-time digitized information to help enforcement. The Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport (DG MOVE) intends to identify and assess different models of smart enforcement systems. Together with FEDeRATED and FENIX projects, aimed at supporting the work of the DTLF group, the implementation of an EU Single Window Environment for Customs is analysed. Furthermore, it is worth to follow the activities of the eFTI4EU project that is aimed at implementing the EU Regulation 2020/1056 relating to electronic information on freight transport (eFreight Transport Information). The eFTI framework could present opportunities to standardize/harmonize data sharing.

To support outreach and engagement activities requested from other tasks of KEYSTONE, a stakeholders’ register in compliance with GDPR rules has been created. The register contains contacts belonging to three main categories of stakeholders: *logistic operators*, *freight terminals* and *enforcement authorities*. These contacts have been collected in an ad-hoc form that will be distributed and promoted for the entire duration of the project. Currently, the KEYSTONE stakeholders’ register counts 15 contacts who will be updated and engaged during the whole period of the project.

To collect needs, requirements, and expectations of a minimum of 300 targeted stakeholders, a survey has been designed and implemented. The main goal of the survey is to identify relevant needs and obstacles that currently affect the controls performed by enforcement authorities on road cross-border logistics. In particular, the survey aims to investigate which kind of data are shared with enforcement authorities and between actors involved in transport operations, which tools are used to exchange data and the current integration of national platforms with the European platforms (e.g. ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI, eFTI platforms, etc.).

To facilitate the compilation of the survey and to increase the number of potential respondents, the survey has been designed totally anonymous. No personal information is collected by the survey and the results are analysed in aggregated form with the goal of gathering the general overview of the compliance checks in the logistic sector. As the survey has been (and will be) distributed around all European countries, a multiple-language survey has been created. The survey was translated from the original English version into other 5 different languages: Italian, Spanish, French, German, and Greek. A multiple-language survey aims to facilitate the compilation of the survey (acceptance rate) and to increase the number of potential respondents (response rate). Furthermore, to make filling out the survey more effective and intuitive, the survey has been designed and implemented in a “conversational” form. The analysis the survey refers to the answers collected in the period 13th of September - 14th of November 2023 (almost two months). The survey is still open and further data will be collected until April (or May) 2024. The analysis aims to collect relevant needs and obstacles that currently affect the controls performed by enforcement authorities on road cross-border logistics. To facilitate the interpretation of the results, each category of stakeholders has been analysed separately. The survey has been filled out by 203 respondents. 91 of them have completed the survey (45% completion rate), with a median compilation time of 5 minutes and 30 seconds.

The main results of the analysis of the survey can be summarised as follows:

- *Language used from respondents.* 35% of respondents filled the survey in English, 30% in Spanish, 27% in Italian and the remaining 8% in German, Greek and French.
- *Geographical location of respondents.* Logistic operators, transport companies and users are in 13 different European countries (Spain, Italy, Slovakia, Romania, Netherlands, Greece, Germany, Finland, Estonia, Denmark, Belgium, United Kingdom, and Austria). Freight terminals are in Italy,

Greece, and Spain. Enforcement authorities are in 13 different European countries (Croatia, Cyprus, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Malta, Netherland, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom).

- *Data and technology role.* Almost all respondents agree that data and technology play a pivotal role in improving and enhancing compliance checks. Only some respondents of the category of “Logistic operator” disagree and indicated as barriers the complex legislation, the cooperation between member states, the geo-political context (e.g., non-EU borders, Brexit, uncertainty of regulations, different languages), and the type of shipping (dangerous or perishable goods, project cargo)
- *Data sharing with authorities.* 57% of terminal and 60% of logistic operators share data. The main barrier for freight terminals for the sharing of data (both with authorities and other actors) is the lack of suitable tools for sharing data.
- *Data sharing with other actors.* 71% of freight terminals and 50% of logistic operators who completed the survey share data. The main barrier for logistic operators is confidentiality and competition factors. The lack of a suitable digital tool is a challenge for logistic operators. They do not share data because it is not mandatory, and they do not have explicit benefits and incomes.
- *Data sharing tools.* No unique platform (national and/or international) exists according to the survey responses. Stakeholders can adopt emails, in-house software and/or commercial tools.
- *Data needs.* All stakeholders who completed the survey are aware of the importance of data and its exchange for enhancing business opportunities. Stakeholders who state they need further data: 85% of enforcement authorities, 71% of freight terminals, 57% of logistic operators.
- *EU platforms.* Freight terminals who completed the survey argue that they have never exchanged information with EU platforms. 17% of logistic operators have used these EU platforms at least once. The most used platforms are IMI and eFTI. No one used Resper. 69% of Enforcement authorities use EU platforms. 23% of authorities do not even know these platforms. TACHOnet and IMI are the most used platforms (over 90% of respondents). According to answers given by the authorities, EU platforms are not linked to each other and must be consulted separately to gain a holistic picture. Authorities suggest integrating the different EU platforms and make them accessible by a single interface. A poor accessibility to EU platforms is also claimed, especially during the roadside checks. Finally, more data should be integrated in the EU platforms.

In conclusion, the analysis of the survey has allowed us to provide relevant insights that will support and guide further investigations during the next activities of the KEYSTONE project. The survey will remain open to achieve at least 300 respondents. The analysis of the answers collected in the period 15th of November - 16th of April (May) 2023 will be included in the deliverable D1.2.

References

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Annex 1 - Privacy policy for the Stakeholder register

Privacy Policy for newsletter, consultation, and coaching activities

The present privacy policy (hereinafter, “Privacy Policy”) applies to all personal data processing that occurs when:

- (i) you interact with any Cefriel employee in the context of the KEYSTONE project;
- (ii) Cefriel communicate with you as part of “stakeholder engagement” operations planned within the KEYSTONE project.

The present policy shall not apply to any other activity out of the scope of the KEYSTONE project. By providing your personal data (e.g., when you complete the form with your contact details) to Cefriel you confirm you have read and understood its methods of collection, processing, use, and disclosure of your personal data as described herein. Any time your consent to personal data processing is required, Cefriel will ask you to confirm your consent to the processing operations in question, as better described herein, ticking the appropriate box for the same. Your consent (provided by ticking the appropriate box) serves as proof that that you have read and accepted the processing operation in question. Documents proving your acceptance of the Privacy Policy, the dates for the same, and any future update to the policy, shall serve as dispositive written proof of your consent. Cefriel process personal data in accordance with applicable data-protection laws and regulations including but not limited to the laws promulgated by the European Union for the regulation of natural person data processing, as well as the free circulation of such data, and all laws promulgated by any EU member state, as well as all orders and guidelines issued by the data protection authority as may from time to time apply, EU Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and Council of 27 April 2016 (hereinafter, “General Data Protection Regulation” or “GDPR”), which supplements national provisions applicable beginning on 25 May 2018 (hereinafter, “Data Protection Laws”).

Who controls the processing of my personal data? Who is responsible for the data?

Data Controller is

1. Cefriel S.c.r.l. with registered office at Viale Sarca 226, Milan, and Tax ID no. 09144820157, phone +39 02.239541, email privacy@cefriel.com, pursuant to Art. 4 of the GDPR.

What personal data are processed?

The processing of your personal data when you fill the form. No other processing is done.

What information do you provide us?

Cefriel process the following categories of data:

- (i) Personal data you provide us when you fill the online form. These personal data include:
 - your first name and surname
 - your email address
 - your company name
- (ii) Personal data you provide when you interact with Cefriel personnel, e.g. when you contact Cefriel researchers for requesting assistance. These personal data may include:
 - your first name and surname
 - your email address
 - your telephone number
 - your professional expertise
 - your company name
 - headquarter location of your company
 - information on the reasons you contacted us
 - correspondence or transcripts / recordings of your interaction with Cefriel staff.

What are the purposes for which my personal data will be processed?

Cefriel will process your personal information for the following purposes:

- (i) manage newsletter subscriptions;
- (ii) to create a list of relevant stakeholders («stakeholder register») to be kept engaged on several KEYSTONE activities (see task 6.2 of the project);
- (iii) to invite you in the participation of different activities (e.g., events, demonstrations, etc.) during all the phases of the project;
- (iv) to welcome your comments and inputs for better addressing the KEYSTONE activities;
- (v) to gather your feedback on the results of the project;
- (vi) to keep you informed about any update and relevant aspect arised from the project;
- (vii) to plan and schedule ad-hoc focus groups, meetings, interviews;
- (viii) to discuss and deepen specific topics that are relevant for supporting several activities within the KEYSTONE project. A not exhaustive list of relevat topics is represented by
 - a. API standardization;
 - b. Plug&Play principles;
 - c. NAPCORE;
 - d. outcomes from other EU projects and/or working groups (e.g., Fenix, Federated, DTLF, ITS, etc.);
 - e. IDSA (International Data Spaces);
- (ix) to support the delivery of the KEYSTONE survey designed for collecting needs and requirements from different categories of stakeholders (logistic operators, carriers, freight forwarders, freight terminals, enforcement authorities, etc.)
- (x) to attend "user evaluation" sessions for testing a web app that will be implemented from KEYSTONE;
- (xi) to contribute to the writing of a White Paper (needs, market perspecitves etc.);
- (xii) to provide, at a national level, information regarding enforcement data collection;
- (xiii) to actively participate in the Multi-Stakeholder Community for replicability analysis;
- (xiv) any other business related to KEYSTONE project ;

What are the legal bases for processing my personal data, as described in this policy?

Cefriel will process your personal data for the purposes described in the Section “What are the purposes for which my personal data be processed?” on one of the following legal bases :

- (i) Reasons relating to Cefriel, or a third party's, legitimate interest - provided such interests do not conflict with your interests, or fundamental rights and liberties (Article 6.1[f] of the GDPR, in effect as of 25 May 2018);
- (ii) Legitimate interests Cefriel might pursue include, to wit, Cefriel interest in responding to your specific enquiries, in requesting your feedback to improve KEYSTONE website and services, or to carry out general marketing activities.

When your specific consent is necessary to process personal data, as described in this document, your personal data will be processed pursuant to such consent.

How long will my personal data be processed?

Personal data shall not be retained longer than necessary to pursue the specific purposes described herein unless a longer retention period is allowed by statute, and shall cease if and when you revoke your consent. Cefriel will keep the data for 5 years after the end of the KEYSTONE project (May 2026).

Is my personal data safe?

Cefriel pledge to protect the security and privacy of your personal data. Cefriel have implemented - and it requires that each service provider and/or third party responsible for any processing done on its behalf to implement, per its instructions - technical and organisational measures intended to prevent the loss or destruction (be it intentional or accidental) of any data, as well as any unauthorised or unlawful use of the data. Furthermore, Cefriel IT infrastructure and software are configured in such a way that personal and identifying data are only used if and when necessary for the specific processing purposes as are, from time to time, pursued. Cefriel use a wide range of technology and advanced security protocols to protect personal data from the above-described risks.

What about data breaches?

If a data breach (Art. 33 and 34, GDPR) occurs, the data controller will alert the control entity designated under Article 55 without undue delay - within seventy-two (72) hours of notice of the breach, if possible - unless it is unlikely that the data breach presents a risk for the rights and liberties of natural persons. Should the report to control entities not be made within seventy-two (72) hours, the report shall include the reasons for the delay. Should the personal-data breach potentially jeopardise the rights and liberties of natural persons, the data controller shall alert the data subject without undue delay.

Where will my personal data go? Who are the intended recipients? Where are data transferred, and for what purposes?

Personal data are collected and then stored in Cefriel servers, or in servers managed by our backup/hosting service providers. All these personal data may be disclosed with the recipients described below. Cefriel disclose your personal data under the terms, conditions, and limits set forth herein, and with your express consent (when and if required) pursuant to Data Protection Laws. Your personal data may be accessed within Cefriel organisation by in-house and external personnel who are duly appointed and trained, and who need to access such data as part of their job duties, and for the processing purposes set forth herein. Cefriel make sure that such persons, directly authorized by Cefriel, are bound to all security and confidentiality duties as required. Your personal data may be accessible to outside service providers Cefriel engage to process personal data on Cefriel behalf, pursuant to Cefriel instructions (as Data Processors). Included among Data Processors are:

External service providers Cefriel engage to provide professional, technical, and organisational services functional to Site management and to all activities carried out through the same. These may include, for example, product sales and related activities, managing the functions offered by the Site and by any programme or service you subscribe to or request via the site, as well as for services narrowly tailored to the processing purposes set forth above. A list of Data Processors and their location is available upon request by emailing privacy@cefriel.com. Data Processors are bound by contract to implement safeguards sufficient to protect personal data security and privacy. Your personal data may be shared with other partners of KEYSTONE project. Cefriel are committed to protecting the security and confidentiality of your personal data by adopting, and requiring any third party responsible for processing your personal data on Cefriel behalf, to adopt, as instructed by Cefriel, technical and organizational measures to prevent the loss and the destruction, even accidental, of data, unauthorized access and illicit or abusive use of data. Personal data shall not be disclosed to third parties for their marketing needs needs neither to social like META, X, INSTAGRAM. The recipients listed supra may be based in a country other than the one in which the personal data was originally collected. Your personal data, however, will be shared within the European Economic Area, in other countries whose ability to provide adequate personal-data protection has been recognised by the European Commission by using SCC (Standard Contractual Clauses).

Must I provide my personal data? What are the consequences of any refusal to submit my data?

Submission of your personal data is optional. Where required pursuant to Data Protection Laws, Cefriel will secure your consent before processing your personal data for the above-cited purposes.

Does the Site contain third-party-controlled elements? Who is responsible for, and liable for, such elements?

The form does not contain links to other sites, neither third-party-controlled objects or elements.

What are my data processing rights, and how might I exercise them?

You have the right, at any time, to exercise those rights recognised under applicable Data Protection Laws including but not limited to: the right to access your personal data, to correct / erase or limit processing on the same, to object (i.e. to opt out of personal-data processing for marketing-related purposes at any time, free of charge), the right to data portability, as well as the right to revoke your consent. Furthermore, you have the right to lodge a complaint with the data protection authority (www.garanteprivacy.it). For a summary of the aforementioned rights and how to exercise them, please review Appendix 1 of this Privacy Policy. For any questions or concerns regarding Cefriel's processing of your personal data, and to exercise those rights established by the Data Protection Laws, please contact us at: privacy@cefriel.com.

Will There Be Updates to the Privacy Policy?

Cefriel reserve the right to update or amend the Privacy Policy, in whole or in part, and at any time, to the extent permitted by law. The most up-to-date version shall be posted to the Site. Should this Privacy Policy be amended, Cefriel shall notify you via a link to the updated policy posted to the Site's home page ("Privacy Policy: Recent updates") and/or by sending you a notice via a different channel (e.g. via email if known and permitted by law).

* * * * *

Appendix 1 - Rights of the Data Subject

As an individual whose personal data is processed in the manner appearing in the present Privacy Policy, you have a number of rights, which are described below. Please note that the exercise of these rights is conditioned on certain terms and criteria set forth in the laws in question.

Rights of Access

To the extent permitted by law, you have the right to obtain confirmation from us on whether your personal data has been subject to processing, and if so, to request access to such data including but not limited to the categories of personal data in question, the purposes for such processing, and the recipients or categories of recipients to whom they were sent. As Cefriel are likewise required to respect the rights and liberties of other parties, such right is not without limits. Should you ask for more than one copy of the personal data subject to processing, Cefriel may charge you a reasonable administrative processing fee.

Right to Correction

You have the right to ask that Cefriel correct any inaccurate personal data implicating you. Furthermore, depending on the processing purpose, you have the right to request incomplete personal data be supplemented. This may be done by submitting an affidavit.

Right to Erasure (the “Right to be Forgotten”)

You have the right to request that your personal data be erased in certain situations, as specified in applicable legislation. If your request falls into that category, Cefriel will work promptly to erase your data. Should Cefriel be unable, for technical/organisational reasons, to erase your personal data, Cefriel will make sure to render them completely and irrevocably pseudonymous, so that Cefriel are no longer in possession of actual personal data implicating you.

Right to Restriction of Processing

In some circumstances - as specified in applicable legislation - you have the right to request that processing on your personal data be restricted. In such cases, your personal data may only be processed (retention is exempted) with your consent or to determine, assert, or defend a right in a court of law, or to safeguard the rights of another natural or legal person, or to pursue a legitimate public interest.

Right to Data Portability

As specified under applicable law, you have the right to receive your personal data (which you provided us according to this privacy policy) in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format, as well as to submit such data (or have them directly forwarded by us) to another data controller, if technically feasible.

Right to Object

Under certain circumstances - as set forth by applicable law - you have the right to object for just cause based on your own particular situation to the processing of your personal data by us at any time. In doing so, you may request Cefriel refrain from further processing of your personal data unless Cefriel can demonstrate cognisable and legitimate reasons for processing that trump your interests, rights, and liberties, or for reasons relating to the determination, assertion, or defence of a right in a court of law, specifically in instances where the processing of your personal data is based on our legitimate interests or for statistical purposes.

Right to Object to Direct Marketing

Should your personal data be processed for direct marketing purposes, you have the right to object to such processing at any time (including to any profiling, to the extent it is related to direct marketing).

Right Not to be Subject to Decisions Based Exclusively on Automated Processing

Except in special circumstances, you have the right not to be subject to decisions based solely on automated processing - including profiling - that have legal consequences for you, or that have a similar, material impact on you as a person.

Right to Withdraw Consent

If you have provided your consent for any data processing as described herein, you may withdraw it at any time with effect for any processing thence forward. The withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of any processing based on consent before its withdrawal. If you wish to access your personal data or exercise any of the aforementioned rights, please send a written request along with a copy of your photo ID to: privacy@cefriel.com. Any correspondence from us regarding your rights as detailed supra shall be provided free of charge. However, Cefriel reserve the right to reject, or charge a reasonable fee for (based on any required administrative processing expenses incurred to provide information, correspondence, or to undertake the requested action) any requests that are patently baseless or excessive (especially when such requests are reiterated). Should you believe that any processing implicating you has been performed in violation of applicable law, you have the right to lodge a complaint with the Data Protection Authority (www.garanteprivacy.it). Please visit that website for the proper forms to file a complain.

Annex 2 - Survey questions

The following tables shows the list of questions for each branch of the survey, defined for each target category (“Logistic operators”, “Freight terminals”, “Enforcement authorities”)

Branch “Logistic operators”

ID question	Topic	Question	Answer
1	Profiling	In which country is your headquarter located?	<i>List of all European country</i>
2	Profiling	Do you carry out international transport?	- Yes - No
3	Data and technology role	Data and technology play a pivotal role in improving and enhancing compliance checks carried out by enforcement authorities, optimising logistics processes and transport sustainability. What's your opinion on this?	- I agree with what you said. A digital transformation should be fostered for enhancing compliance checks - I have a different opinion. A digital transformation is important but other aspects should be properly considered
3.1	Data and technology role	<i>[3. I have a different opinion. A digital transformation is important but other aspects should be properly considered]</i> Please, specify which aspects (not directly related to technology) should be taken into consideration for improving the checks	<i>Open question</i>
4	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	Do you currently share your data with enforcement authorities?	- Yes, with all the authorities - Yes, but only with some authorities - No, data is not shared
4.1	Data sharing with	<i>[4. Yes, but only with some authorities]</i> Please, specify which authorities you share data with	- Road police - Customs - Finance police - Port authorities

	enforcement authorities		- Other
4.2	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	<i>[4. No, data is not shared]</i> Please, specify why you do not share data	Open question
4.3	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	<i>[4. Yes, but only with some authorities]</i> <i>[4. Yes, with all the authorities]</i> Which platforms do you use for sharing data?	Open question
4.3.1	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	<i>[4. Yes, but only with some authorities]</i> <i>[4. Yes, with all the authorities]</i> Which kind of data do you share?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driver (e.g. professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times) - Operator (e.g. authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good reputation, risk score) - Vehicle (e.g. technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections) - Cargo (e.g. types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing) - Operation (e.g. type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular) - Transport status forecast and actual data (e.g. train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep) - Yard situation (e.g. stock, capacity) - Other

5	Data sharing with actors	<p>The exchange and the sharing of information with the authorities and in general with other actors (e.g., other logistic operators, freight terminal operators, public authorities, etc.) can improve your productivity and efficiency. For example, the existing freight marketplace platforms help logistic operators avoid empty running.</p> <p>Please, let us know, do you share (even only partially) your data with other actors?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, data is shared automatically by digital and integrated platforms - Yes, data is shared manually and by not-integrated platforms - No, currently data is not shared but I'm interested in exploring that chance - No, currently I'm not interested in sharing data
5.1	Data sharing with actors	<p><i>[5. Yes, data is shared automatically by digital and integrated platforms]</i></p> <p>Please specify which platforms are used</p>	Open question
5.2	Data sharing with actors	<p><i>[5. Yes, data is shared automatically by digital and integrated platforms]</i></p> <p><i>[5. Yes, data is shared manually and by not-integrated platforms]</i></p> <p>Which kind of data do you share?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driver (e.g. professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times) - Operator (e.g. authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good reputation, risk score) - Vehicle (e.g. technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections) - Cargo (e.g. types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing) - Operation (e.g. type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular) - Transport status forecast and actual data (e.g. train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep)

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yard situation (e.g. stock, capacity) - Other
5.3	Data sharing with actors	<p><i>[5. No, currently data is not shared but I'm interested in exploring that chance]</i></p> <p>Please, specify why you do not share data</p>	Open question
5.4	Data sharing with actors	<p><i>[5. No, currently I'm not interested in sharing data]</i></p> <p>Please, specify why you are not interested in sharing data</p>	Open question
6	Data needs	In the previous questions we focused on data that you provide to other actors. Now, please, think about data you might need from them. Is there any data, currently not shared with you, that might be helpful?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, some data would be really helpful - No, further data is not needed
6.1	Data needs	<p><i>[6. Yes, some data would be really helpful]</i></p> <p>Please, specify which data (e.g. traffic data, delays, etc.)</p>	Open question
7	EU platform	To facilitate the cooperation for cross-border enforcement, the EU has developed several IT systems allowing for secure communication and transfer of data. In particular, ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI and eFTI platforms. Have you ever exchanged information with one (or more) of these European platforms?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, I have - No, I haven't
7.1	EU platform	<p><i>[7. Yes, I have]</i></p> <p>Please, specify which EU platform</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ERRU - TACHOnet - Resper - IMI - eFTI platforms - Other EU platforms
7.1.1	EU platform	<p><i>[7. Yes, I have]</i></p> <p>Is it your platform integrated with the EU platforms?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, it is - No, it isn't
7.1.1.1	EU platform	<p><i>[7.1.1. Yes, it is]</i></p> <p>Do you need any improvement?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No
7.1.1.1.1	EU platform	<p><i>[7.1.1.1. Yes]</i></p> <p>Please, specify which kind of improvement</p>	Open question
7.1.1.2	EU platform	<p><i>[7.1.1. No, it isn't]</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes - No

		Do you deem worthful any integration between EU platforms and your tools?	
7.1.1.2.1	EU platform	<i>[7.1.1.2. Yes]</i> Please, specify better your needs	<i>Open question</i>

Branch "Freight terminals"

ID question	Topic	Question	Answer
1	Profiling	In which country is your headquarter located?	<i>List of all European country</i>
2	Profiling	Do you carry out international transport?	- Yes - No
3	Profiling	Which multimodal transfers do you manage?	- Road transport - Rail transport - Air transport - Sea transport
4	Data and technology role	Data and technology play a pivotal role in improving and enhancing compliance checks carried out by enforcement authorities, optimising logistics processes and transport sustainability. What's your opinion on this?	- I agree with what you said. A digital transformation should be fostered for enhancing compliance checks - I have a different opinion. A digital transformation is important but other aspects should be properly considered
4.1	Data and technology role	<i>[4. I have a different opinion. A digital transformation is important but other aspects should be properly considered]</i> Please, specify which aspects (not directly related to technology) should be taken into consideration for improving the checks	<i>Open question</i>
5	Data sharing with	Do you currently share your data with enforcement authorities?	- Yes, with all the authorities - Yes, but only with some authorities

	enforcement authorities		- No, data is not shared
5.1	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	<i>[5. Yes, but only with some authorities]</i> Please, specify which authorities you share data with	- Road police - Customs - Finance police - Port authorities - Other
5.2	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	<i>[5. No, data is not shared]</i> Please, specify why you do not share data	Open question
5.3	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	<i>[5. Yes, but only with some authorities]</i> <i>[5. Yes, with all the authorities]</i> Which platforms do you use for sharing data?	Open question
5.3.1	Data sharing with enforcement authorities	<i>[5. Yes, but only with some authorities]</i> <i>[5. Yes, with all the authorities]</i> Which kind of data do you share?	- Driver (e.g. professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times) - Operator (e.g. authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good reputation, risk score) - Vehicle (e.g. technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections) - Cargo (e.g. types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing) - Operation (e.g. type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage, cross-trade, occasional, regular) - Transport status forecast and actual data

			<p>(e.g. train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yard situation (e.g. stock, capacity) - Other
6	Data sharing with actors	<p>The exchange and the sharing of information with the authorities and in general with other actors (e.g., other logistic operators, freight terminal operators, public authorities, etc.) can improve your productivity and efficiency. For example, information about possible delays (e.g., truck or train in arrival at the terminal) can be mutually shared between the terminal and the truck thus improving the scheduling of the boarding process.</p> <p>Please, let us know, do you share (even only partially) your data with other actors?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, data is shared automatically by digital and integrated platforms - Yes, data is shared manually and by not-integrated platforms - No, currently data is not shared but I'm interested in exploring that chance - No, currently I'm not interested in sharing data
6.1	Data sharing with actors	<p><i>[6. Yes, data is shared automatically by digital and integrated platforms]</i></p> <p>Please specify which platforms are used</p>	Open question
6.2	Data sharing with actors	<p><i>[6. Yes, data is shared automatically by digital and integrated platforms]</i></p> <p><i>[6. Yes, data is shared manually and by not-integrated platforms]</i></p> <p>Which kind of data do you share?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Driver (e.g. professional competence, authorization, records of driving, working and resting times) - Operator (e.g. authorization to engage in a profession and to operate on the market, good reputation, risk score) - Vehicle (e.g. technical condition of the vehicle, its weights and dimensions, registration, conformity, required inspections) - Cargo (e.g. types of goods, authorization for carrying specific goods, cargo securing) - Operation (e.g. type of operation: domestic, bilateral, cabotage,

			cross-trade, occasional, regular) - Transport status forecast and actual data (e.g. train arr/dep, trucks arr/dep) - Yard situation (e.g. stock, capacity) - Other
6.3	Data sharing with actors	<i>[6. No, currently data is not shared but I'm interested in exploring that chance]</i> Please, specify why you do not share data	Open question
6.4	Data sharing with actors	<i>[6. No, currently I'm not interested in sharing data]</i> Please, specify why you are not interested in sharing data	Open question
7	Data needs	In the previous questions we focused on data that you provide to other actors. Now, please, think about data you might need from them. Is there any data, currently not shared with you, that might be helpful?	- Yes, some data would be really helpful - No, further data is not needed
7.1	Data needs	<i>[7. Yes, some data would be really helpful]</i> Please, specify which data (e.g. traffic data, delays, etc.)	Open question
8	EU platform	To facilitate the cooperation for cross-border enforcement, the EU has developed several IT systems allowing for secure communication and transfer of data. In particular, ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI and eFTI platforms. Have you ever exchanged information with one (or more) of these European platforms?	- Yes, I have - No, I haven't
8.1	EU platform	<i>[8. Yes, I have]</i> Please, specify which EU platform	- ERRU - TACHOnet - Resper - IMI - eFTI platforms - Other EU platforms
8.1.1	EU platform	<i>[8. Yes, I have]</i> Is it your platform integrated with the EU platforms?	- Yes, it is - No, it isn't
8.1.1.1	EU platform	<i>[8.1.1. Yes, it is]</i> Do you need any improvement?	- Yes - No

8.1.1.1.1	EU platform	<i>[8.1.1.1. Yes]</i> Please, specify which kind of improvement	<i>Open question</i>
8.1.1.2	EU platform	<i>[8.1.1. No, it isn't]</i> Do you deem worthful any integration between EU platforms and your tools?	- Yes - No
8.1.1.2.1	EU platform	<i>[8.1.1.2 Yes]</i> Please, specify better your needs	<i>Open question</i>

Branch "Enforcement Authorities"

ID question	Topic	Question	Answer
1	Profiling	In which country are you located?	<i>List of all European country</i>
2	Profiling	Which kind of enforcement authorities describes you better?	- Road police - Customs - Finance police - Ministry - Public authority (e.g. sea port authority) - Other
2.1	Profiling	<i>[2. Other]</i> Please specify better	<i>Open question</i>
3	Profiling	What rules do you enforce?	- Driving/rest times - Cabotage - Posting of workers - Roadworthiness - ADR (International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Road) - Weight and Dimensions - Customs - Other
4	Data and technology role	Data and technology play a pivotal role in improving and enhancing compliance checks	- I agree with what you said. A digital

		carried out by enforcement authorities, optimising logistics processes and transport sustainability What's your opinion on this?	transformation should be fostered for enhancing compliance checks - I have a different opinion. A digital transformation is important but other aspects should be properly considered
4.1	Data and technology role	<i>[4. I have a different opinion. A digital transformation is important but other aspects should be properly considered]</i> Please, specify which aspects (not directly related to technology) should be taken into consideration for improving the checks	<i>Open question</i>
5	Data needs	Is there any data, currently not shared with you, that might be provided by the stakeholders (e.g., logistic operators, terminal/freight operators, authorities of other countries, etc.) and that might improve your checks?	- Yes, some data would be really helpful - No, further data is not needed
5.1		<i>[5. - Yes, some data would be really helpful]</i> Please, specify which data (e.g. traffic data, delays, etc.)	<i>Open question</i>
6	Platforms	Which are the main platforms you currently use for carrying out the controls and compliance checks?	<i>Open question</i>
7	Platforms	Should these platforms be improved and enhanced?	- Yes, the platforms should integrate further data sources (e.g. foreign data sources) - Yes, for other reasons (e.g. accessibility) - No, further improvements are not needed
7.1	Platforms	<i>[7. Yes, the platforms should integrate further data sources (e.g. foreign data sources)]</i> Please, specify better which data sources should be integrated	<i>Open question</i>
7.2	Platforms	<i>[7. Yes, for other reasons (e.g. accessibility)]</i>	<i>Open question</i>

		Please, specify better the possible improvements	
8	EU platform	To facilitate the cooperation for cross-border enforcement, the EU has developed several IT systems allowing for secure communication and transfer of data. In particular, ERRU, TACHOnet, Resper, IMI and eFTI platforms. Do you use one (or more) of these platforms for carrying out your checks regarding international transportation?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Yes, I use these platforms (at least one) - No, I don't use these platforms but I know them - No, I don't know these platforms
8.1	EU platform	<i>[8. Yes, I use these platforms (at least one)]</i> Which ones do you use?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ERRU - TACHOnet - Resper - IMI - eFTI platforms - Other EU platforms
8.1.1	EU platform	According to your experience, how these platforms should be improved and enhanced?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - By synchronizing and integrating the EU platforms with my tools - By integrating the different EU platforms and making them accessible by a single interface - By the improvement of the EU platforms' accessibility (especially for roadside checks) - By making the EU platforms more user-friendly - By enriching the data currently provided by the EU platforms - By providing new data sources via an existing or a new EU platform - No improvement is needed, the EU platforms already satisfy our needs - Other
8.2	EU platform	<i>[8. No, I don't use these platforms but I know them]</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - They are not accessible/available

		Please, specify for which reasons you don't use these platforms	(especially during roadside checks) - They are difficult to use - They do not provide relevant information for controls/checks - Other
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